

ON THE ISSUE OF THE USE OF HISTORICAL KNOWLEDGE IN INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS

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Abstract.

The article focuses on improving the scientific research work carried out on reforming the education and education of our youth in our country from a scientific point of view at the present time, which is the development of society, as well as on the issues of using historical knowledge in increasing the social activity of students.

Keywords: social activism, activism, historical knowledge, student, educator, upbringing, education, science.

"As long as we have decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we will rely on two solid pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values".¹

In fact, citizens who felt that the new Uzbekistan was guided by the above thoughts of the head of our state to a new stage of development and was guided by the reforms in this country, contributed to the responsible task of building a new Uzbekistan from the current modern educator in the establishment, in this regard, he sought spiritual perfection, comprehensive perfection from the educational system of the state, requires the education of individuals capable of Independent Education and self-development. This requires each Specialist to become a mature specialist in his profession in order to get a decent place in the labor market in the current complex threatening situation. It requires a high level of knowledge and spiritual excellence from the teacher, if it assumes professional competence from employees of all industries. This places a particular responsibility on institutions of higher education that have grown future pedagogical teachers. In the development of future educators as a mature specialist, it will be wrong not only if he does not know his specialty science, but also his History Past and present.

Updating all areas of history on the basis of digital technologies, modernizing the teaching of history according to the program "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" and strengthening competitiveness, will create even wider opportunities for the introduction of advanced technologies in the field.

History is the science of Man, the study of society as a product of human activity. It follows from this that the task of historical science is to fully study, state the historical process. In the study of our past history, direct historical sources are consulted and historical events are analyzed and clarified through sources, historical Osori-atikas, etc. Information Communication Technologies, which have become an integral part of our life as a result of the technical achievements of science, have changed society over the past 30 years. It has been giving us

¹ Ш.М.Мирзиёев. <https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/shavkat-mirziyoev>

lightness and comfort in all aspects of our lives. Updating all areas of history on the basis of digital technologies, modernizing the teaching of history according to the program "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" and strengthening competitiveness, will create more wide opportunities for the introduction of advanced technologies in the field.

This requires the acquisition of systemic knowledge related to the worldview, knowledge of current issues of public policy, independent analysis of socio-political issues and processes taking place, the ability to independently think in one of the foreign languages to have knowledge of historical knowledge, to form immunity against ideological and information attacks. In developed countries, it focuses more on combating external and internal threats. One of the external threats to Uzbekistan is lagging behind in the field of development and implementation of advanced technologies. One of the most important factors in the stabilization of educational development, especially in the issue of competitive personnel in the demand for time, is the provision of continuity in the organization of history education in the pre - school, general secondary, professional and higher education systems and raising it to a new level.

The relevance of the new worldview or reforms carried out in our country largely depends on raising education and upbringing to a high level with the demand of the current period, the formation of a comprehensively mature harmonious person. The scientific research work carried out on reforming the education and education of our young people in our country from a scientific point of view at the moment of the progress of society requires improvement based on the demand of today. Uzbekistan has entered a new stage of development on the principle of "from national recovery to national rise". The intensity of the new era puts its clear strict requirements on the educational system. In the quality education of young people, it is advisable to use the achievements of national and modern pedagogy and develop new pedagogical technologies. The reason is that the socio-economic, ideological and spiritual and cultural environment in our country presupposes the upbringing of a new generation of Uzbekistan, capable of ensuring the great future of our state, perfectly occupying the foundations of historical knowledge, able to think independently, whose family, national traditions are most importantly loyal to their homeland. The fact that a student of pedagogical higher education, as a future teacher-coach, has an independent opinion, which means, first of all, having mastered historical knowledge and comparing them with comparison, to extract the only correct truth from them is to instill it in his own mind, to be able to live from this conclusion. That is why we are the task of researchers-to encourage our young people to gain knowledge, call for activity is to show the importance of the knowledge acquired in each type of future activity and, in addition to improving the competencies of social activity, to pay special attention to the development of their independent qualifications. "The upbringing of the younger generation has been in the spotlight of thinkers all over the world all the time."² The New opened a new era in the implementation of the idea of providing education to the growing generation in the essence of the content of all reforms carried out in Uzbekistan. In fact, as we noted earlier, while pedagogical higher education students, as future teachers, remain not only profoundly familiar with their specialty, it is also darkur who analyzes the history of the emergence, development of this discipline, the perfect knowledge of the history of what people did, who massively contributed to the improvement of science. This is a matter on which

² Қори Ниёзий "Ҳаёт мактаби", "Фан" нашриёти 1966 йил, 152 бет

historical knowledge depends. This is an important factor for all areas of Education. The teacher must constantly stand a few heads higher than his students, otherwise he will not have a reputation in front of the children, because unexpected questions can be left without the teacher being able to answer. Therefore, the interpretation of pedagogical higher education becomes a socially active student in all respects if, in addition to specialist knowledge, he also acquires historical knowledge. Historical knowledge plays a big role in this. For example, a student specializing in musical education is asked "Who Do you know from musical composers?" when asked, it is clear that they will immediately say the answers Beethoven, Mosart. But it is the commandment that Yunus Rajabiy, Thothasin Jalilov or Abduhoshim Ismailov and other composers, who have now made a great contribution to the development of our classical musical art, will also remember. This is due to the fact that in the science of music he did not study our past musicians or did not know our national history well. By widely promoting the study of our national historical heroes, historical knowledge is assimilated in students, and through it becomes a socially active student. Currently, the development of social activity in the future life of students who have not studied the past, values of their home country may be slow. It is also a bit of a challenge that such students can aspire to the future and live with ambition on the path of a particular goal. At present, when ideological threats are escalating, improving the social activity of students of pedagogical higher education as future teachers is concerned about the prospect of a new Uzbekistan; having a good understanding of the dignity of himself and his homeland, it is to preserve it, to work in the face of high ideas, new discoveries, intentions, to raise his talent, the opportunity to have, if necessary, his soul in the spirit of the prospect of the land, the happiness of Eli. Improving the social activity of students with historical knowledge means understanding the world in the interests of our national independence. In the acquisition of historical knowledge, not only during history lessons, the use of digital technologies in history education, the use of e-books on history education, the use of multimedia applications of history books also have a great effect. By studying history through modern methods-acquire systematic knowledge related to the worldview, know the basics of the socio-humanitarian Sciences, current state policy issues, can independently analyze social problems and processes.

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